

ISic0098

I.Sicily inscription 0098

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

breccia

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico

Baldassare Romano

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line

1
: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to

2
: mm

Text

1. [---]io Sex[---]
2. [equopublic]o · praef(ecto) · fabr(um) [trib(uno)milit(um)]
3. [le]g(ionis) XII [Ful]minatae · pro [legato]
4. Caesari[s] Cypri · praef(ecto) · c[o]h[ort] [(is)] [---]
5. equitatae et · Iulia [e] [---]
6. M(arcus) · Livius · Macedonic[us] [---]
7. l(ocus) [d(atus) d(ecreto) d(ecurionum)]

Apparatus

Text based on ILTermini

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285316

EDR 127534

EDCS 22100052

Bibliography

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Manganaro, G. 1988. *La Sicilia da Sesto Pompeo a Diocleziano. ANRW.* 2.11.1: 3-89. At 53 n.259, cf 10 n.23, 42

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